

Work Life Balance of Women Faculty Working In HEIs with Special Reference to Bangalore City

Dr. Mathiyarasan M.¹, Dr. Chandrakhanthan J.², Mr. Dhanapal C.³

^{1,2,3} Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Kristu Jayanti College, Autonomous, Bangalore.

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
21 February 2023

ABSTRACT

Women are demonstrating greater passion and interest in the educational area as technology advances, and they are finding it increasingly difficult to balance their personal and professional lives. The importance of a faculty member in educational institutions' productivity cannot be overstated. To provide a high-quality service, they must be mentally and physically fit. The role of a faculty is very significant for the productivity of educational institutions. The majority of academics are women. As a result, it's crucial to observe how these women manage their job and personal lives. In this context, the paper analyses the work life balance challenges faced by women faculty working in HEIs and impact of work life balance on women faculties' performance in HEIs by using primary data. Through a literature analysis, the study chose three important factors that were appropriate for the study scenario. Workload, social support, and childcare were chosen as independent variables, whereas work life balance was chosen as the dependent variable. The primary data was collected via a standardized questionnaire by the researchers. In this article, a survey of 35 Bangalore educational institutions is undertaken using a sample of 220 instructors to determine the true state of work-life balance. The study finds that the work-life balance situation for female faculty members is moderate, which can be improved by providing flexible working hours, transportation, residential facilities, child care centers, flexible work arrangements/job sharing, reduced working hours and workload, and child schooling. The result of the research will be helpful for the HEIs administrators, to identify the importance of work life balance of female faculty in order to improve the outcome of their institutions.

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Mathiyarasan M.

KEYWORDS: Work Life Balance, HEIs, Work Environment / Culture.

INTRODUCTION

From an identity confined to kitchen and daily household chores, to an identity in IT and other sectors of labor, the role of girls has changed drastically. But, the sole difference between the 2 genders is that men are more accessible to concentrate only on work compared to women. For her, it's tougher due to the normal mindset of handling both works inside and out of doors home. Hence, this is often resulting in an imbalance between the private and business life of women. So, within the motive of earning enough for the betterment of her family, the work life dominates her personal life. As a result, it results in social hazards like increase within the number of divorces and infertility thanks to stress in work. At times women get subjected to high level of stress, that they're more prone to undergo depression and other mental issues. It's been observed that a lady can work well before marriage but this consistency changes after marriage and tends to vary until her retirement. So within the rise of this issue, many

organizations have come to the fore for the betterment within the dual lifetime of women. This permits her enjoy both of her lives and attain a level of satisfaction. Women who are professionals face tons of trouble removing the barriers and building bridges with reference to balancing between home and work. From time, immemorial women had to cross tons of obstacles to realize an edge in society. But with the advancements within the fields of education and mindset, they were ready to overcome the obstacles. A piece life balance is often achieved during a women's life only she is in a position to enjoy and achieve in both personal and business life. All this is often resulting in a rise within the job opportunities of women. This has given many ladies an aspiration to their personal development.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify work life balance challenges faced by women faculty working in HEIs.

- To examine the impact of work life balance on women faculties performance in HEIs.

RESEARCH GAP

So far many researchers did the research on work life balance of employees and productivity and some of them found various factors contributing to work life balance. This research study concentrates female faculty working in higher educational institutions how they balance with their work and life.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Social media usage also is a factor that impact on work-life balance (Kumar & Priyadarshini, 2018). Emotional intelligence, time management, nature of the spouse, awareness, and organizational support have positive impact on work-family balance and work stress has negative impact on work family balance (Samson & Sareena Umma, 2019). Further child care responsibility, elderly dependency is negative association with the work-life balance and partner or spouse support, colleague support and job resources are positive connection with WLB, but number of working hours does not have a significant impact with the work-life balance of Sri Lankan academics (Pathirana & Pathirana, 2020).

Due to demographic and workplace changers such as: transformation in family structures, growing reluctance for 'long number of hours' acceptance culture, greater number of women in the workforce and technological advancement. All these may result in the employees having difficulty in prioritizing between their work roles and their personal lives (Obiageli et al, 2015).

Kumarasamy et al., (2015) found that emotional intelligence, job engagement and organizational support positively related with work life balance and technology advancement and work overload are negatively related with work life balance. Emotional intelligence means ability to understand and manage people and ability to act wisely in managing human relations (Thorndike, 1920 cited in Kumarasamy et al., 2015). Jothi Sree and Jyothi (2012) found that emotional intelligence plays an important role in female work life balance (cited in Kumarasamy et al., 2015).

A.K.M.Mominul Haque Talukder (2011) studied work life balance in service context and made attempts to identify how employees are balancing their work life by considering variables such as work culture, job satisfaction, employee benefits, work environment, flexible work time, work load and discrimination. He identified that work life balance is influenced by all these variables.

A.G.V.Narayanan & R.Lakshmi Narayanan (2012) worked, on 200 human resources working in Tamilnadu IT organizations and found that work timings, excess work load, long travel, routine meetings, work on holidays are strongly influencing work life balance of employees.

Rana Zehra Masood & Seema Mahalwat (2012) worked on 300 employees working in different banks and insurance companies in Haryana region and suggested that work place flexibility, reduction of work time, leave and benefits, dependent care initiatives and work life stress management reflect the importance of nurturing a supportive culture in terms of embarrassing work life balance concepts. They also advised that the organizations which neglect the recent trends and changes regarding demographic variables related to employee work life balance will end up with employee lower productivity.

Santha Lakshmi.K & Dr.N.Santhosh Kumar (2011) studied 250 women employees at SRM University and found that working women undergo severe stress as they try to balance their domestic life and Professional life. They revealed that continued work under pressure would result in poor performance at the institution as well as domestic life.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Managing a home while raising young children when both spouses are employed outside the house is challenging and stressful. Balancing work commitments with life commitments involves a myriad of trade-offs for two-income families with children, it also provides ongoing challenges for adults who remain single or don't have children. Mid-life workers often affect balance issues from two ends of the spectrum; young children and ageing parents. This issue, however, includes women faculties beyond those that have children. Many ladies' faculties are choosing to remain unmarried, but still have critical and valuable commitments outside work. Therefore, there's a requirement to spot work life balance challenges faced by women faculties working in HEIs. Therefore, this study focused the research problem as "what are the challenges of work life balance of female faculties?"

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher used Descriptive study in this research. The study was conducted in Bangalore city. The total sample size is 220. The researcher used convenience sampling method to collect data. Data collected through primary and secondary data. The researcher has used structured questionnaire to collect the data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Factors affecting the work life balance

Factor	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank
Satisfaction about work place environment	3.586	0.831	2
Individual and family happiness	4.137	1.269	1
Balance of personal and work life	3.106	1.093	4
Frequency of work life conflict	2.881	1.237	5
Organizational support for work life balance	3.373	0.977	3

Issues faced by Women

Issues faced by Women	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Work Environment			2		1
Flexible Work Time			2	1	
Work Load	32	2			1
Pressure of Accreditations	35		2	1	
Goal of Higher Education	2	2	2		
Job Satisfaction	4	2		1	
Care Giver Strain	3	2	1	2	
Role Overload	28	1		1	2
Organizational Culture	24	2	1		
Multiple Roles	26	1	1	1	1
Financial Problems	6	2			
Family Commitments	19	2	1	1	
Total	179	16	12	8	5

It is inferred from the above table that majority of the respondents are responded that pressure of accreditations is major issue faced by them. Followed by work load, role

overload and multiple roles. The institution must focus on this point and reduce this issues.

The influence of Family on Work

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
My personal or family life has kept me concerned from doing a job.	20	22	45	90	43
My family is/are obliging to maintain a work life balance.	15	109	44	33	19

It is inferred from the above table that the respondents responded that their family is not influenced on work. They

also responded their spouse / parents / family are cooperating to maintain the work life balance.

The influence of Work on Family

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
My job has kept me concerned from giving helpfulness to my family.	11	25	109	43	32
My organization/ colleagues are supportive to sustain a work life balance.	16	124	45	16	19

It is inferred from the above table that the respondents responded that their job is disturbed them from giving attention to their family. They also responded that their organization / colleagues are support them to maintain work life balance.

CONCLUSION

It is clear that the obligations towards the families and expectations of the institution and constant struggle to take care of a balance of labor can have serious implications on the lifetime of an individual. Work and private life conflict occurs when the burden, obligations and responsibilities of labor and family roles become incompatible. Therefore, it's important for workers to take care of a healthy balance between personal and their professional lives. This may help them achieve their personal and professional goals also the organization they're working for. Therefore it's reasonable to conclude that the fashionable organizations, especially educational institutions, should address the Work Life Balance related issues and problems among their staff, specifically women & take a holistic approach to style and implement policies to support the teaching staff to manage their work life balance which might increase the performance of those staff members.

REFERENCES

1. Asher, R. (2011), *Shattered: Modern Motherhood and the Illusion of Equality*, Random House, London.
2. Better Balance, Better Business: Alberta Human Resources and Development, ISBN 0-7785-1606-7, Retrieved October 11, 2012 from <http://alis.alberta.ca/pdf/cshop/betterbalance.pdf>
3. Blyton, P. and Dastmalchian, A. (2006), “Work-life integration and the changing context of work”, in Blyton, P.,
4. Blunsdon, B., Reed, K. and Dastmalchian, A. (Eds), *Work-Life Integration: International Perspectives on the Balancing of Multiple Roles*, Palgrave, Basingstoke.
5. Booth, A.L. and van Ours, J.C. (2005), *Hours of Work and Gender Identity: Does Part time Work Make the Family Happier?*, Centre for Economic

Policy Research, Australian National University, Canberra.

6. Broad bridge, A. (2008), “Barriers to ascension to senior management positions in retailing”, *Services Industries Journal*, Vol. 28 Nos 9/10, pp. 1225-45.
7. Burke, R.J. (1994a), “Females on corporate boards of directors: views of Canadian CEOs”, *Women in Management Review*, Vol. 9 No. 5, pp. 3-10.
8. Burke, R.J. (1994b), “Females on corporate boards of directors: forces for change?”, *Women in Management Review*, Vol. 9 No. 1, p. 27.
9. Cassell, C. (1997), “The business case for equal opportunities: implications for females in management”, *Women in Management Review*, Vol. 12, pp. 11-17.
10. Deery, M., (2008), *Talent management, work-life balance and retention strategies*, *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management* Vol. 20(7), pp. 792-80
11. Eikhof, D., Ruth., (2012), *A double-edged sword: twenty-first century workplace trends and gender equality*, *Gender in Management: An International Journal* Vol. 27 (1) , pp. 7-22
12. Ezra, M. and Deckman, M. (1996), “Balancing work and family responsibilities: flexitime and child care in the federal government”, *Public Administration Review*, Vol. 56 No. 2, pp. 174-9.
13. Fleetwood, S. (2007), “Re-thinking work-life balance: editor’s introduction”, *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 18 No. 3, pp. 351-9.
14. Ford, M.T., Heinen, B.A. and Langkamer, K.L. (2007), “Work and family satisfaction and conflict:a meta analysis of cross-domain relations”, *Journal of Applied Pyschology*, Vol. 92 No. 1, pp. 57-80.
15. Friedman, D.E. (1992), “Linking work-family issues to the bottom line”, Report No. 962, The Conference Board, New York, NY.